

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HIKMATI****FIRST NAME: SHAHZAD****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Formatted:** Font colour: Dark Blue**Commented [KG1]:** Do not change the formatting of the template!**Formatted:** Font colour: Dark Blue**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 0%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 5-7 critical concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your R.P.)

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 6-13)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
3. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)
6. CMS CRIB SHEET (EUCLID 2024, 43-50)
7. Latin **A**bbreviation and **E**xpressions (EUCLID 2024, 58-65)

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ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing standard English is one of the most challenging tasks for international students at the Ph.D level. These challenges appear in educational background, academic writing level, linguistic differences, cultural differences, support and resources, psychological factors, and technological tools. This response paper will explore the insights of (EUCLID 2024), offered on developing the skills necessary to excel in writing standard English at the Ph.D. level.

This resource under exploration is “Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma, 2024, ACA-401/ACA-401D. Coursepack: Period 1. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.” This vital work explains most of the strategies needed for essay writing in academic settings. By presenting the key themes and skills outlined in this version, the author will examine the different parts that count as the foundation for the academic level of proficiency.

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Then, I focused on ACA401D Period One's two instructional tutorials. They detailed the critical parts of the successful response paper's writing, including a strong structure, consistent content, and detailed different heading styles. Both tutorials stressed the importance of a strong-sentence preliminary, followed by a well-developed structure aligned with EUCLID University criteria. By following these strategies, I gained a deeper understanding of organizing my thoughts for well-drafted response papers, which show fundamental academic writings. These tutorials improved my proficiency in writing response papers. As a result, both of them are essential for my writing development.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

Chapter I of the coursepack provides instructions on how to lead my response papers. It outlines essential preparations, practical tips, and advice on preparing effective skills for different parts of essays, for example, in

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the introduction, body, and conclusion of response papers. It highlights the importance of proper planning, allocating sufficient time early, and maintaining a structural writing plan. These recommendations enhanced my writing abilities, resulting in well-organized papers (EUCLID 2024, 7).

Understanding the essay topic is the first important step, followed by researching and reading the needed literature to develop an academic essay (EUCLID 2024, 8). I noted that during this process, it is essential to ask questions, make notes, and highlight critical information that will help throughout the writing process. In addition, allocating sufficient time to analyze the sources helps the process. The provided method of essay writing will strengthen and enhance essay credibility.

(EUCLID 2024, 9), defines good essay writing as a balance of creating and critical thinking. Creative thinking widens the scope of ideas through techniques like brainstorming and mind mapping, whereas critical thinking narrows the focus, ensuring each example's relevance to the argument. A well-rounded essay needs diverse information and viewpoints from multiple sources. Evaluating these essays contributes to the depth and credibility of writing.

Next, for academic writing, following a structured method is essential throughout the process. As EUCLID (2024, 10) introduces a well-structured essay introduction, body, and conclusion. This approach facilitates a coherent flow of ideas. I understood that the fundamental aspect of essay writing involved many tasks. By advancing these requirements, I can explore the essay in a way that enhances my writing skills. Therefore, comprehension of the response papers' scope is essential for writing insightful essays.

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For writing an academic essay, including the required references and using the other authors' ideas is essential to avoid plagiarism. I noted that specific referencing style by EUCLID University response papers. However, EUCLID accepts another referencing format (EUCLID 2024, 1). I know that proper loyalty to referencing supports academic integrity and improves my work's credibility.

Finally, I noticed that when writing an essay, the topic sentence should clearly state an idea to set a focused direction for the essay—for example, concentrating on evaluating the critical aspect of a theory and describing its relevant parts without trying to attempt a comprehensive overview. In addition, avoiding broad generalizations for clarity with short sentences, structured paragraphing, and simple language is a better choice. I noted that using style, avoiding passive sentences, and considering counterarguments to ensure complexity are better choices for academic writing. After completing the response paper, read it loudly to ensure it follows well. Avoiding plagiarism, proper quoting, and refereeing should be used (EUCLID 2024, 11-14). Following the above guidelines will improve writing quality and essay integrity.

However, I also faced a disagreement throughout the EUCLID (2024), which is a need for different types of essay writing, such as descriptive, narrative, expository, and persuasive. A Ph.D. student should have sufficient knowledge of the four types of essay writing and, most importantly, when and how to use them.

3) PUNCTUATION

Chapter II of EUCLID (2024) highlighted the different punctuation marks used in English and response paper writing, especially for PhD students. Their clarity and precision enhance the credibility of academic writings. I learned that using effective and accurate punctuation marks communicates the ideas well so that the readers will get essential perspectives related to the rigorous evaluation of response papers (EUCLID 2024). This section emphasized the different punctuation rules in academic and professional writing to maintain coherence, creditability, and clarity and facilitate scholarly communication.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

Chapter EUCLID (2024) explains that it first accepts the difference between American and British English by stating that since World War II, American English has risen globally, reflecting the U.S.'s political, economic, technological, and cultural influence. This variation of U.S English now plays an essential and leading role in determining "world English," in contrast to British English in many areas as the key factors contributing to this dominance included the U.S.'s significantly larger population of native speakers, its economic power, and the wide spread of its higher education system. In addition, the widespread influence of the United States mass media and culture, combined with the U.S.'s powerful international politics and economic standing, further strengthens this trend. Considering these differences, American and British English remains similar, particularly in academic and scientific contexts (EUCLID 2024). Therefore, the differences between standard American and British English hold different significance, reflecting the evaluation of English as a global language.

5) PILGRIMS

Based on EUCLID (2024, 24-34), avoiding “plagiarism” is crucial in academic writing to ensure the integrity and originality of others’ work. I understand that plagiarism occurs when someone uses someone else’s ideas and words without acknowledging their source. This could include quoting, paraphrasing, or copy-pasting the text from the internet or other resources without giving them credit and mentioning the proper citation. Further, by understanding this, I will adhere to ethical writing as a Ph.D. student and contribute to the credibility of others’ work. Subsequently, I recognize and will avoid plagiarism and adapt myself with honesty and respect at the academic level.

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Citing properly and crediting authors is essential when incorporating quotes, phrases, statistics, or visuals from the sources. The source is not just conventionalist; it recognizes the originality of the author’s work, which is both unethical and unfair, as it unethically takes credit for someone’s work. In addition, plagiarism is an academic offense that leads to significant consequences. Hence, consistently crediting other sources is crucial to maintaining integrity and fairness in an educational context (EUCLID 2024, 34).

6) STYLE GUIDE

According to Chapter V of EUCLID (2024), a style guide is essential for consistency in writing across many disciplines, including technical writing, business communication, journalism, and web copywriting. I learned that such guides aligned with academic writing standards, publications, or websites rather than just reflecting an individual author’s preferences. Moreover, this is important for organizations. For example, EUCLID (2024, 41) recommends using the Chicago Rules (Turabian) and provides related templates and guidelines to help the students of EUCLID University in standardized style guidelines. I learned that by following a standardized style guide, I can produce better response papers during my studies.

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Then, using the style guide is essential for clarity in the writing process at most levels. Based on my understanding from EUCLID (2024), it is true that essay writing takes into consideration specific guidelines. I noted that styles include more than just grammar rules, and punctuation includes the aspect of sentence length, the layout of manuscripts, font usage, spelling differences, audience, abbreviation, terminology, symbols, voice preference, structure, paragraph formatting, and headings (EUCLID 2024, 41). This proves the practical need for a style guild in different writing contexts.

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Finally, I noted that a style guide is essential for proposal writers and freelancers who must develop detailed guides on demands. I have many years of experience writing proposals in humanitarian and development and demonstrating the ability to adhere to a set style while learning from feedback that can significantly enhance the written content. Furthermore, I noted that creative writers also benefit from using a style guide as it can save time for proofreading, revising, and editing. By leveraging these guides, the writer can achieve higher reliability and quality in their work in the academic setting.

7) CMS CRIB SHEET

The Chicago style (CMS) and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers significance, as detailed in EUCLID (2024, 47-53), lies in their compressive and flexible approaches to formatting in academic and professional writing. These referencing guides provide a standardized approach to citing sources, structuring documents, and presenting information clearly and reliably. I noted that this consistency is vital for academic writing, enabling the readers to trace sources quickly and verify the credibility of the research conducted. I acknowledged that the difference between Chicago and Turabian styles primarily lies in their methods. Where Chicago Style assists a comprehensive variety of publishing needs, Turabian precisely adjusts these guidelines for students and researchers. Therefore, mastering the mentioned styles equips scholars with tools to produce standard-based research papers, smoothing academic communication and contributing to enhancing knowledge.

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8) LATIN ABBREVIATION AND EXPRESSIONS

Chapter VII emphasizes the significance of using primary language in academic and technical writing, especially when dealing with Latin abbreviations. It provides two tables outlining standard Latin abbreviations and expressions and advises using English equivalents in business, formal, and technical writing. This is to ensure understanding. For example, instead of a Latin abbreviation, use terms like "for example," "and "so on" to promote a new term. I noted that this chapter advocates for plain language, a direct and robust style without condescending, using short sentences and simple terms while avoiding jargon, acronyms, and abbreviations. Finally, this chapter advanced my effectiveness in using plain language that should be visually appealing, logically organized, and easily comprehensible on the first reading, ultimately enhancing clarity and efficiency.

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9) CONCLUSION

As I wrap up this exploration, it is clear that academic writing needs more studying and practical writing; it is a thoughtful journey that transforms skills and experience. This process requires more time, practical skills, the best support, and efforts to listen to others. I learned that integrating these insights from various perspectives can improve my confidence in writing academic papers. These steps I explored became evident that "practice makes perfect."

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

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Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.